

Ayitbaeva Shokhista Kuvondik

Student of the Faculty of Foreign Languages of Nukus State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract: Today, the attitude towards the Uzbek language is not very positive. People's linguistic wealth is getting poorer and poorer. It is being replaced by social network slang and inappropriate Russian words.

Key words: Uzbek language, era of globalization, rich scientific heritage, research works.

As this year marks the 31st anniversary of the adoption of the Law "On State Language", we feel its practical value more and more. This historical document proves to be a significant step to restore the status of the Uzbek language, which is the product of many centuries of cultural, scientific, educational and artistic thinking. According to UNESCO, there are currently 6,909 languages in the world, and about 200 of them have the status of a state language. How deeply our grandfather Navoi described the charm, beautiful expression, emotion and elegance of our language, and in the last century, representatives of literature Abdulla Kadiri, Cholpon, Oybek, Gafur Ghulom, Abdulla Oripov, Erkin Vahidov, Ozad Sharafiddinov contributed to enriching it with their works. The rich scientific heritage left by such enlightened leaders is honored and respected today.

Indeed, today the Uzbek language is reflected in all official documents as the state language, and extensive efforts are being made to develop it. By the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 21, 2019 "On measures to fundamentally increase the prestige and position of the Uzbek language as a state language" No. PF-5850, this date was recognized as the "Day of the Uzbek language holiday". [1] In addition, within the framework of the implementation of this decree, the activities of the Department of State Language Development of the Cabinet of Ministers have been established, with the aim of organizing state control over the development of the state language by state bodies and organizations, including local executive authorities, and the observance of laws on the state language. the position of adviser on issues of increasing efficiency, ensuring compliance with laws on the state language was introduced. This also serves to conduct business in the state language. "Whoever wants to feel all the grace, charm and power of the Uzbek language, and its limitless possibilities, should listen to the legends of our Munis mothers, our thousand-year-old epics, our immortal statuses, and listen to the magical songs of our bakhshi and hafiz," said President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, saying that the Uzbek language was granted the status of the state language. in his speech at the 30th anniversary ceremony. [2]

Over the past period, a lot of practical work has been done to develop the Uzbek language, to preserve its purity, to increase the prestige of the state language as a language of science, and to fully teach young people. In 2006-2008, a five-volume "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" was published. The edition of the dictionary in the Latin alphabet is being prepared these days. It is expected to contain 100 thousand words.

But how effective is it? Are we feeling the effects of this in society? What is the attitude towards the language not only among young people but also among adults?

Today, the attitude towards the Uzbek language is not very positive. People's linguistic wealth is getting poorer and poorer. It is being replaced by social network slang and inappropriate Russian words. Although new technological terms are coming in from abroad and enriching our vocabulary, none of us feel the responsibility to value our own language more than it does. True,

in the era of globalization, we need foreign words, but it will not hurt to think about creating and using Uzbek alternatives.

Advertising banners on the streets, store fronts, foreign names of household service outlets, and mistakes written in Uzbek are criticized by our intellectuals who are lovers of the language, and it is not without reason.

Why don't we love our language, learn to appreciate it. After all, how many of our grandfathers, Abdulla Avloni, Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov, and Mahmudhoja Behbudi, did not dress a century ago? What if the problems of the century have not changed? Our great writer Abdulla Qadiri said, "The Uzbek language is not poor, those who call it poor are poor. "They should not transfer their ignorance to the Uzbek language," he said. As a linguist, Mahmudhoja Behbudi wrote articles such as "Not two, but four languages are necessary", "Every nation is proud of its own language", "Language issue", "The word Sart is unknown", "The word Sart was not known".[3] While the process of preparation of scientific articles and dictionaries is still going on, they remain only papers, the impact of which is not known due to the fact that the mechanisms of bringing it into the people have not been developed.

Linguist scientist Bakhtiyor Mengliev wrote in "Marifat" newspaper, "Creating corpora of the Uzbek language in our country is not satisfactory. The scientific research conducted in this field is only at the stage of developing the theoretical foundations of Uzbek corpus linguistics and creating a couple of corpus records as an example," he wrote. [4] Why is corpus linguistics, a booming field in the last decade, faltering? I think this is one of the aspects that we have to deal with.

Language is our identity, it embodies our values. It enters our blood with mother's milk. We communicate in Uzbek, express our thoughts, laugh, cry. Language is an image of who we are.

But starting from the family, even when we go to our office, if we don't add a single foreign word, we don't feel free, as if we are demonstrating our "competence". This problem indicates that we do not read books or newspapers and magazines, and our vocabulary is poor. After all, if we communicate with our child who grew up watching Uzbek cartoons at home, we will be surprised by the literary words in his pronunciation, right? So, pure Uzbek shows, artistic-literary books will undoubtedly serve to enrich our language.

When it comes to language, it would not be wrong to include the issue of literacy and beautiful writing as an issue. We have to read over and over again to understand the words of our boys and girls who are typing on social networks, it is very difficult to select the ones who write beautifully among the students of the higher education institution. Therefore, while we are talking about the purity of the language and its beauty, we should strictly control the literacy of students from the first period of education - from school, and consider it our main task to raise them to be educated.

Each office has a specific department that deals with documents. The most frequently observed language problems occur in the activities of this department. For example, if the office writes a letter to a certain organization, or receives some document, the methodological problems in it will be clearly visible. Today, one of the most urgent issues is this - one of the most important and urgent issues in the formation and improvement of Uzbek documentation is the issue of the language and style of documents. Every leader, employees of management institutions, in a word, people whose activities are involved in the preparation of work documents, should know Uzbek spelling, punctuation marks and stylistic rules thoroughly and perfectly. Otherwise, documents

will be accepted piecemeal, piecemeal, piecemeal, or we will write in Russian and translate it into Uzbek.

Recently, I read on the website of the Committee on International Relations and Friendship with Foreign Countries under the Cabinet of Ministers that interest in learning the Uzbek language is growing in the Netherlands. [5] A meeting was held at the Embassy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Kingdom of Belgium on the issue of supporting the interest in learning the Uzbek language in European countries. Of course, this is worthy of attention.

It is not good for us to be apathetic and indifferent at a time when foreigners are interested in learning our language.

I will conclude with the following poem by the poetess Zulfia Mominova, who proudly wrote about language:

There is no one greater than you for me,
My mother tongue is a corrupt king.
If you are there, then there is an Uzbek,
My mother tongue is Olympanohim.

List of used literature

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoev. We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people. T., Uzbekistan, 2017.
2. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on wide celebration of the thirtieth anniversary of the adoption of the Law "On the State Language" of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent, October 4, 2019.